

PHYSICAL STRUCTURE OF METALS IN RELATION TO THEIR CATALYTIC BEHAVIOUR. PART I. LANGMUIR SURFACES

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Metals with face-centred cube lattice structure and high vibrational energy at their melting points are good catalysts.

Langmuir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 2221) extended Bragg's work on crystals to chemical reactions taking place in heterogeneous systems. Surface atoms in a solid possessing residual affinities constitute a "checker board" where gases or adsorbed molecules may anchor on till chemical action or desorption takes place. He considered metal surfaces like platinum and tungsten and showed theoretically and experimentally that simple reactions like the dissociation of hydrogen molecules into atoms could be well accounted for. He has further shown that the atoms in a metal catalyst though vibrating about a centre are held rigidly (*Phys. Rev.*, 1916, 8, 149) and there is no gradation of layers of atoms varying in density from the solid to the gas surrounding, but the change from the solid to the gas is abrupt and adsorption is mono-molecular in thickness. His experiments conclusively proved his theory.

Taylor (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, 108A, 105) put forward a theory of active centres on the evidence of (i) lack of correlation between catalytic activity and adsorption, (ii) the extraordinary heat sensitivity of the catalyst material (Smith *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 121, 1613; 1923, 123, 2088), (iii) the poisoning of catalysts in stages (Vavon and Husson, *Compt. rend.*, 1922, 175, 277), and (iv) very great variations in the energy of adsorption of gases for different parts of the surface (Garner and Blench, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1288). Reserving a detailed examination of these points to later communications, it has to be observed, that most of the work on catalysis deals with complex reacting substances and also different types of solid substances as catalyst materials. Mono-atomic metals, semi-conductors, ionic valence type crystals and amorphous substances have all been used. It is not surprising therefore that the simple idea of Langmuir had to be modified. In this paper, assuming the Langmuir surface is basically correct, an attempt has been made to review the physical properties of metallic types of solids in relation to their catalytic behaviour. The physical properties of different types of solids are different from each other, and arise from their structure. In the conclusions arrived at here, a certain amount of empirical factor is unavoidable but their usefulness must be conceded only from the large number of cases they reasonably cover.

Types of Structures

Most of the metals belong to one of the three types: B.C.C., F.C.C. and C.P.H. The adsorption of reacting molecules takes place through the valence forces of the surface atoms.

In Table I are summarised some of the physical characteristics of metals belonging to different groups. It is noticeable that most of the metals usually used in different reactions as catalysts are F.C.C. types and then a few C.P.H. types. In the conversion of benzene into *cyclohexane* by metal catalysts, Long, Frzer and Ott (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1101) found that B.C.C. structures were inactive while the F.C.C. ones were active.

TABLE I-

Metals.	Type of lattice.	M. p.	$m^2 \nu^3 \times 10^{-21}$.	$t_r \times 10^{-18}$.	$t_r / 6\lambda$
<i>Group I</i>					
Copper	F.C.C.	1356°K	105	4.2	4.7×10^{-4}
Silver	F.C.C.	1234	104*	3.5	2.5×10^{-4}
Gold	F.C.C.	1336	107	4.8	2.7×10^{-4}
<i>Group II</i>					
Magnesium	C.P.H.	934	75	..	..
Calcium- α	F.C.C.	1123	83	..	..
Calcium- β	C.P.H.	"	..	..	..
Strontium	F.C.C.	1044	85	..	..
<i>Group III</i>					
Aluminium	F.C.C.	933	74	..	8.3×10^{-4}
Lanthanum- α	C.P.H.	1085	93*	6.6	..
Lanthanum- β	F.C.C.	"	..	..	..
Thallium- α	C.P.H.	576	34*	..	..
Thallium- β	F.C.C.	"	..	..	..
<i>Group IV</i>					
Titanium	C.P.H.	2073	165	..	..
Tin- α (grey)	T.C.	505	39	22.2	8.2×10^{-4}
Tin- β (white)	B.C.T.	"	"	"	"
Tungsten	F.C.C.	1953 to 2053	169	..	..
Lead	F.C.C.	600	48	33.6	1×10^{-4}
<i>Transition group</i>					
Vanadium	B.C.C.	1993	156	..	..
Chromium- α	B.C.C.	2103	137	23.9	3.3×10^{-3}
Chromium- β	C.P.H.	"	"	"	"
Manganese- α	Cubic	1515	117	..	..
Manganese- β	Complex	"	..	..	..
Manganese- γ	Tet, F.C.	"	..	..	..
$\alpha\beta\gamma$ -Iron	B.C.C.	1808	142	20.64	2.9×10^{-3}
γ -Iron	F.C.C.	"	..	"	"
Cobalt- α	C.P.H.	1763	140	23.73	3.2×10^{-3}
Cobalt- β	F.C.C.	"	..	"	"
Nickel- α	C.P.H.	1725	136	27.97	3.8×10^{-3}
Nickel- β	F.C.C.	"	..	"	"
Rhodium	F.C.C.	2239	..	..	..

TABLE I (contd.)

Metals.	Type of lattice.	M. p.	$mr^3 \nu^3 \times 10^{-22}$.	$t, \times 10^{-18}$.	$t, /6\lambda$.
Palladium	F.C.C.	1827	133	22.39	2.2×10^{-3}
Tungsten- α	B.C.C.	3643	212	7.52	...
Tungsten- β	F.C.C.	"	212	"	...
Osmium	C.P.H.	2973?	207	...	...
Iridium	F.C.C.	2827	195	25.69	2.1×10^{-3}
Platinum	F.C.C.	2046	162	18.78	1.4×10^{-3}
<i>Non-metal</i>					
Graphite			278	120.6	6.0×10^{-3}

- Note*:—(1) The m.p. s. are taken from Kaye and Laby ("Physical and Chemical Constants", 1944).
 (2) $mr^3 \nu^3 \times 10^{-22}$ from Srikantan (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1930 **4**, 540).
 (3) $tr = 3k/hd$ where K is the Boltzman's constant and h , heat conductivity of solids (*Metals Hand-book*, 1939) and d is distance between the atoms (Seitz, "Modern Theory of Solids", 1940).
 (4) λ the reciprocal of atomic frequency ν (Lewis, "Physical Chemistry", 1921, III, p. 6r).
 (5) The peculiarity of iron is discussed under allotropic changes.
 * These values have been recalculated.

Energy of Vibration of Atoms

In Table I, there are a few exceptions to the conclusions drawn above. Calcium (α), strontium, aluminium, thallium and lead are not preferred as catalysts, though they are F.C.C. in type. They may enter into chemical reactions and may even act as catalytic poisons. Lead, for example, is not a catalyst but is known to poison active materials. It appears therefore that the availability of greater number of atoms in the surface or lattice planes is not the only factor of importance, but these atoms must be capable of activating the adsorbed molecules. The author has shown (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1930, **4**, 539) that the energy of vibration ($4\pi mr^3 \nu^2$) of an atom is a matter of decided importance in catalysis. (The terms are explained in the paper cited). It is to be noted that F.C.C. or C.P.H. lattice metals, which have a value for this ($mr^3 \nu^3$) energy term below 100×10^{-22} exhibit low catalytic activity. Thus aluminium, thallium(β) and lead, though F.C.C. in type, have low values for energy of vibration of atoms and are not catalytic. There are also other metals having a high value but not F.C.C. types. They are not also catalysts. Therefore the above conclusion could be modified that all metals having F.C.C. structures and vibrational energy of their atoms more than $4\pi 100 \times 10^{-22}$ are good catalysts.

In the last column in Table I ($t, /6$), $t,$ gives the time necessary for the temperature increment of the surface layer of one of the faces of a cube of a metal to fall to 37% of its initial value (Langmuir, *loc. cit.*) and λ is the time of oscillation of an atom, for the various metals. The metals of the non-transitional group are 1000 times more rigid than graphite, while those of the transitional group are only 100 times so. It is not surprising therefore that catalysts are to be chosen more often from the transitional group than from other groups.

Allotropic Changes

Metals of the transition group exhibit the phenomena of allotropism at ordinary pressures. The most important are iron, cobalt and nickel. A change in physical characteristics, and hence a change in catalytic properties, is to be expected from these allotropic modifications of the metals. α -Tungsten is of B.C.C. type and β -tungsten is of valence type of crystal and its activity is similar to that of graphite. In fact that adsorption on tungsten surfaces is akin to chemical compound formation (Chemisorption) is evident from the work of Langmuir (*loc. cit.*). The nature of the lattice planes in α -iron is exceptional though α -iron is of B.C.C. type it would show some catalytic properties. The B.C.C. form is stable between 0° and 1179°K and between 1674° and 1808°K , while γ -iron is stable between 1179° and 1679°K . Most of the prepared iron catalysts are in the B.C.C. region. However, Risen-hut and Kaupp (*Z. physikal Chem.*, 1928, 133, 459; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1930, 36, 392) find that on adsorption of nitrogen the B.C.C. type changes to F.C.C. in the case of iron. The work of Fischbeck (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1934, 40, 517) on the decomposition of ammonia by iron shows increased activity as the iron changes to γ -form *i e.*, F.C.C. type.

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